

THE ROLE OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT AND PEER-LED EVALUATION IN SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** The article presents an overview of research on the problem of developing self-esteem of primary school students in Chinese The People's Republic. The conditions and means of developing self-esteem of younger schoolchildren are analyzed, recommendations are formulated for the development of self-esteem of younger schoolchildren, the ability to independently choose types of activities and plan individual tasks, keep records of the results completed tasks, demonstrate the results of self-assessment and engage in communication with peers and the teacher.*

***Key words.** Comprehensive assessment, self-assessment, Chinese elementary school students, self-development*

Introduction

Conditioned by the adoption of the State Council In 2020, the document "General Plan for deepening the reform of education assessment in a new era" emphasizes the need to reform assessment system of Chinese primary schools to solve the main problems in the process of assessing the quality of students' education, which is related to fostering students' responsibility for their self-development. At this stage, the main problems existing in assessing the quality of education of Chinese schoolchildren are related to the fact that excessive attention is paid to the functions of selecting the best students for schools, academic performance, exam results, rather than methods of evaluating the quality of education and improving the quality assessment system and the development of

younger schoolchildren; issues of developing students' motivation for educational activities, their individual characteristics.

In the research, scientists have identified the importance of students' self-esteem in the context of a comprehensive assessment as a personal understanding of the results of educational activities and an emotional attitude towards them, which determines the upbringing of independence, responsibility, reflection of a younger student. Some scientists have noted that the self-assessment of students is a personal realistic objective self-description formed on the basis of realistic records. Some scientists have proposed starting formation of students' self-esteem with the comprehensive assessment process at school: Realistic records of the learning process; self-assessment of results in various activities, their demonstration; self-assessment in semester reports; selection and ordering of educational material and student records according to self-developed assessment criteria; establishment of their own growth points" - all these link to achieve the goal of a comprehensive assessment of the quality of education . Scientists agree that it is an effective method of assessing the quality of education in the context of a comprehensive assessment in general. One of the buzzwords in the practices of assessment for English learning is peer- and self-assessment as a part of school-based assessment. In Malaysia, this school-based assessment practice has been researched among the instructors in secondary schools, higher education, and primary schools. Peer- and self-assessment is useful yet difficult to practise in a primary school classroom due to young students' limited understanding. Moreover, in-depth research on this practice of assessment for learning is still scarce (Black, 2015; Black & Jones, 2006). English assessment practices were regularly surveyed and found to be at basic level. (Rothinam, 2023; Sathasivam et al., 2019). Therefore, peer- and self-assessment practices in primary schools for the English language are necessary.

Conclusion. Thus, It is important for students to identify the positive dynamics of their development and reflect on weaknesses and shortcomings. The purpose of

self-assessment in semester reports is to analyze and summarize past experiences, carry out self-reflection, detect progress and eliminate shortcomings. Therefore, students not only pay attention to their academic performance, but also evaluate all aspects of their personality in order to receive timely help from parents, and teachers.

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